

Impact of Marketing on the Use of Social Networks on Innovation, Customer Satisfaction and Growth of Fast Food Companies in the Municipality of Tota, Boyacá

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Abstract: Digital transformation has renewed business dynamics, especially in highly competitive sectors such as fast food. This study analyzes the impact of the use of social networks on innovation, customer satisfaction and the growth of fast food companies in the municipality of Tota, Boyacá. With a quantitative and descriptive approach, a questionnaire was applied to 30 companies to measure the adoption of digital strategies, interaction with customers and the effect on operational and commercial management. The results reveal that most companies use social networks as a driver of innovation and to adapt to change, in addition to attracting customers through 100% relevant content. Digital campaigns increase visibility and sales, while order management and staff training have been optimized thanks to these platforms. The role of authentic communication and the promotion of organizational well-being in sustaining growth is also highlighted. It is concluded that social networks are indispensable tools for the competitiveness and sustainability of these companies, recommending strengthening digital training, diversifying communication strategies and optimizing internal processes to consolidate their development in an increasingly digital and demanding market.

Keywords: Social Media, Innovation, Customer Satisfaction, Digital Marketing and Business Growth

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1. Introduction

The digital age has brought about profound changes in business dynamics and in the way companies interact with their customers, especially in highly competitive sectors such as fast food. In local and regional contexts such as the municipality of Tota, Boyacá, the strategic incorporation of social networks is positioned as a key resource for innovation, product promotion and consumer loyalty. Social networks, by offering direct and dynamic channels of communication, have transformed the way organizations manage their presence in the market, allowing not only the effective dissemination of messages and offers, but also the rapid adaptation to changes in the environment and the construction of sustainable relationships with their audiences (Díaz Calle et al., 2024) (TerriData , 2024) (Lozano-Torres et al., 2021) (Mera-Plaza et al., 2022)

Various studies have emphasized that the digitization of the market is not only a trend, but a strategic necessity for companies to survive and grow in saturated and demanding markets. In particular, for micro, small and medium-sized fast food companies, the efficient use of relevant content, exclusive promotions and interactive formats such as live broadcasts becomes a competitive differentiator that contributes to increasing both visibility and customer satisfaction. In addition, digital management facilitates internal processes such as order management, staff training and improvement of the work environment, fundamental elements for organizational sustainability (Caro-Moscoso et al., 2021) (Shocking -Condori & Molina Díaz, 2020) (Caro-Moscoso et al., 2021; Shocking -Condori & Molina Díaz, 2020; Mera-Plaza et al., 2022) .

The main problem facing this research lies in the insufficient understanding and diagnosis of how fast food companies in the municipality of Totade Tota strategically use social media to empower innovation, manage customer satisfaction and achieve sustainable growth. This lack limits the development of strategies adapted to the particularities of the local context, preventing businesses from being able to fully take advantage of the benefits of these digital platforms, effectively face competition and respond to the changing demands of their consumers. Likewise, there is a gap in knowledge about the implementation of clear and SMART objectives, the effectiveness of digital advertising campaigns and the practices of well-being and training of personnel through digital social tools, determining aspects for continuous improvement and business competitiveness in rural environments (Romero Medina & Mesías Cabezas, 2022) (Zambrano Macias, 2022) .

The importance of this research lies in contextualizing the transformative role of social networks within a rural and semi-urban environment, where companies face particular challenges in terms of resources, training and access to technology. Understanding how these institutions use digital platforms to innovate, adapt and meet

user demands is essential to design policies and strategies that strengthen their local economic positioning and development. Likewise, reflecting on the implementation of clear and SMART objectives (S: Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Temporary) in these companies can increase the effectiveness of their digital initiatives and contribute to sustained growth in the competitive food sector. (Cobo, 2020) (Janssen, 2024)

Justifying this research involves acknowledging the growing influence of social media on the local economy and the need to provide a theoretical and practical framework that guides fast-food companies on how to leverage these tools to boost their innovation, management, and organizational well-being. By providing evidence and analysis focused on the specific reality of Tota, Boyacá, this study contributes to closing gaps in the existing literature on digitalization in regional contexts, offering valuable perspectives for entrepreneurs and academics interested in sustainable business development in rural areas. (Lozano-Torres et al., 2021) (Shocking - Condori & Molina Díaz, 2020)

Therefore, the general objective of this research is to analyze the impact of the use of social networks on innovation, customer satisfaction and growth of fast food companies located in the municipality of Tota, Boyacá. To fulfill this purpose, the following specific objectives have been proposed: to evaluate the degree of innovation and adaptation to change through the integration of social networks in business operations; analyze the digital strategies implemented for customer attraction and satisfaction; identify successful practices in order management and customer service through social media; determine the impact of advertising campaigns and the use of SMART objectives on business results; and explore actions aimed at strengthening the well-being and training of staff through digital platforms.

2. Conceptual and theoretical framework

The conceptual and theoretical framework of this research on the impact of the use of social networks in fast food companies located in the municipality of Tota, Boyacá, is built from key concepts and theories related to digital marketing, communication in social networks, strategic management based on SMART objectives, and organizational innovation. contextualized in the gastronomic sector.

2.1 Digital Marketing

It is the set of strategies, techniques, and tools that allow companies to promote their products or services through digital channels. In the field of fast food, digital marketing translates into the creation of relevant content, exclusive promotional campaigns for social networks, and the use of segmented advertising to attract and retain customers. In addition, digital marketing makes it possible to measure the impact

of advertising actions in real time, facilitating decision-making and adjusting strategies. (Merino Cava & Valdiviezo Sir, 2022) (Pilco-Román, 2020)

Digital marketing has revolutionized the way companies establish contact with their markets, moving from one-way communication to two-way, interactive and personalized communication. In the fast food sector, this transformation is especially significant, given that today's consumer demands speed, quality and differentiating digital experiences. (Merino Cava & Valdiviezo Sir, 2022) (Arregocés-Mendoza, 2020)

2.2 Social Media

Defined as digital platforms that facilitate interaction, communication and content generation between users and organizations. Through social media, fast food companies can create communities around their brands, build emotional relationships with consumers, and engage in conversations that influence perception and purchase decision. In addition, these platforms allow direct sales, personalized attention and dynamic dissemination of promotions and events. (Hugo Cardenas et al., 2019) (Shocking -Condori & Molina Díaz, 2020) (Hugo Cardenas et al., 2019)

Social networks have been studied as platforms that enhance efficient communication and create lasting bonds between brands and customers. Studies show that the positive impact on sales and loyalty is associated with the ability of these platforms to generate viral content, manage feedback and enable direct service channels (Hugo Cárdenas et al., 2019) (Pilco-Román, 2020) .

2.3 Fast food

A concept that describes food prepared and served in short times for immediate consumption, characterized by convenience and accessibility. The fast food sector is distinguished by high competitiveness, constant changes in consumer preferences and the need for agile marketing strategies to maintain relevance and growth. (Benítez Díaz, 2021) (Shocking -Condori & Molina Díaz, 2020)

2.4 SMART Goals

Methodology for the definition of specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and temporary goals. Its application in digital campaigns ensures efficient planning, rigorous monitoring and evaluation of results, enhancing the effectiveness of marketing initiatives and business growth. (Janssen, 2024)

The inclusion of SMART objectives in the design and evaluation of digital strategies makes it possible to overcome improvisation and orient actions towards concrete and measurable results in the short and long term. This is essential in a market as competitive and changing as the fast food market. (Velasco-Arias & Cevallos-Campoverde, 2023)

2.5 Innovation and Organizational Well-Being

Innovation is understood as the process of implementing new ideas, products, or processes that generate value, while organizational well-being includes policies and practices that promote the physical and mental health of staff and improve internal culture. In the digital context, these dimensions are integrated to promote the sustainability and competitiveness of companies. (Castro-Martínez & Díaz-Morilla, 2021)

Organizational innovation, supported by digital technology, also influences the internal structure of companies, improving processes, promoting continuous training and guaranteeing a work environment that favors the productivity and commitment of the team. This comprehensive approach underpins the ability to adapt and sustain growth in the digital environment. (Castro-Martínez & Díaz-Morilla, 2021)

3. Methodology

This research is framed within a quantitative and descriptive approach, aimed at analyzing the impact of the use of social networks on innovation, customer satisfaction and growth of fast food companies located in the municipality of Tota, Boyacá. This approach allows the relationship between the use of digital platforms and business results in this sector to be accurately measured and described. (Bernal-Torres, 2016; Hernández-Sampieri et al., 2014)

The population under study was made up of fast food companies operating in the municipality of Tota. A sample of 30 companies was selected through non-probabilistic sampling for convenience, given the accessibility and willingness of these businesses to participate in the study. (Bernal-Torres, 2016; Hernández-Sampieri et al., 2014)

A structured questionnaire was designed and applied that includes closed questions aimed at measuring aspects related to digital innovation, social media marketing strategies, customer management, order optimization and staff training. The questionnaire was validated through peer review and a pilot test to ensure its relevance and reliability. (Bernal-Torres, 2016)

Data collection was carried out through face-to-face and telephone surveys, guaranteeing informed consent and confidentiality of the information collected. Subsequently, the data were tabulated and analyzed using descriptive statistical tools such as frequencies, percentages, and measures of central tendency, which allow identifying patterns and trends in the use and exploitation of social networks by the companies studied.

A quantitative descriptive analysis was used to evaluate the prevalence and degree of implementation of digital strategies and their relationship with innovation, customer satisfaction and business growth. In addition, a comparison was made between different practices implemented to identify the most effective. (Hernández-Sampieri et al., 2014)

Compliance with fundamental ethical principles was ensured throughout the research process, including respect for the privacy of company owners and employees,

the exclusive use of information for academic purposes, and the guarantee of anonymity in the presentation of results. (Bernal-Torres, 2016)

4. Results

The analysis of the results obtained from the 30 fast food companies in the municipality of Tota, Boyacá, reveals clear trends regarding the impact of social networks on different business dimensions, such as innovation, customer satisfaction, operational management and increased sales.

Innovation and Adaptation to Change

A high percentage of companies (83.3%) indicated that social networks have driven innovation processes in their businesses, while 93.3% said they have adapted to change thanks to the integration of these platforms. This suggests that social media is not only a communication tool, but also a catalyst for transformation and continuous improvement in business operations.

Board 1

Innovation and Adaptation to Change of Fast Food Companies

<u>Aspect</u>	<u>Yes (%)</u>	<u>No (%)</u>
Innovation through networks	83.3	16.7
Adapting to change	93.3	6.7

Note. Prepared by the authors

Customer Attraction and Persuasion

The attraction of customers through digital content was total (100% affirmative), evidencing that the development of relevant content is crucial to capture attention. Persuasion through offers achieved 73.3% acceptance, as did the use of stories or live broadcasts to convince the target audience.

Board 2

Customer Attraction and Persuasion in Fast Food Companies

<u>Attraction/Persuasion Tool</u>	<u>Yes (%)</u>	<u>No (%)</u>
Attraction to content	100	0
Convince with offers	73.3	26.7
Convince with stories/live streams	73.3	26.7

Note. Prepared by the authors

Customer Satisfaction and Communication

The social media interactions that generate the most satisfaction include likes (86.7%) and comments (60%), followed by direct messages (40%). Authentic communication, through sharing stories and experiences, also stands out with an 86.7% acceptance rate. Offering exclusive content and special promotions had 50% support, while online events and surveys received lower participation.

Board 3

Customer Satisfaction and Communication

Type of Interaction/Communication	Frequency	%
I like it	26	86.7
Feedback	18	60
Direct Messages	12	40
Sharing stories and experiences	26	86.7
Exclusive Content/Promotions	15	50
Online Events	7	23.3
Polls in stories	11	36.7

Note. Prepared by the authors

Impact of Advertising Campaigns

66.7% highlighted that the campaigns significantly boosted sales. In addition, 60% expressed an improvement in visibility and positioning while the increase in web traffic was indicated by 26.7%. Positive comments by campaigns received 43.3%.

Board 4

Impact on Advertising Campaigns

Impact of Advertising Campaigns	Frequency	%
Increased sales	20	66.7
Better positioning	18	60
Increased web traffic	8	26.7
Positive feedback	13	43.3

Note. Prepared by the authors

Strategies for Increasing Sales

The most common strategies include publishing content with direct links (50%), using carousel ads (36.7%), and exclusive discounts for social networks (40%). Shopping made easy with payment integrations had 30%, and only 6.7% use live shopping with special discounts.

Board 5

Strategy to increase sales

Social Media Sales Strategy	Frequency	%
Publish content with links	15	50
Carousel Ads	11	36.7
Exclusive discounts	12	40
Purchase with integrated payment	9	30
Live Shopping Events	2	6.7

Note. Prepared by the authors

Optimization and Training

The optimization and management of orders through social networks had a high percentage of implementation (96.7%). Training for operational improvement and service was recognized by 70%. In addition, practices to promote employees' physical and mental well-being, such as flexible schedules and positive organizational culture, were highly valued.

Board 6

Social media order optimization and training

Area	Frequency/Yes	%
Social media order optimization	29	96.7
Training for efficiency	21	70
Flexible schedules and remote work	22	77.3
Positive organizational culture	17	56.7

Note. Prepared by the authors

These results demonstrate that Tota's fast food companies are significantly leveraging social media for innovation, customer engagement and satisfaction, as well

as to boost their sales and optimize operability. However, there are spaces to strengthen training and expand strategies such as live shopping events that still have low adoption. This analysis invites us to strengthen actions aimed at authentic communication and training to increase the competitiveness and sustainability of the sector in increasingly demanding digital scenarios.

5. Discussion

The results of this research show that social networks are a decisive tool for innovation and growth in fast food companies in the municipality of Tota, Boyacá. The high proportion of companies that report innovation (83.3%) and adaptation to change (93.3%) through the use of these platforms coincides with previous studies that highlight the transformative role of digital marketing in the competitiveness and agility of businesses. This finding confirms that social networks are not only communication channels, but also mechanisms for the constant updating and improvement of business processes. (Pilco-Román, 2020) (TerriData , 2024) (Shocking -Condori & Molina Díaz, 2020; Romero Medina & Mesías Cabezas, 2022) (Hugo Cardenas et al., 2019; Merino Cava & Valdiviezo Sir, 2022)

Customer attraction through relevant content obtained unanimous acceptance (100%), reflecting the importance of generating information that connects emotionally with consumers, according to the theory of content marketing. In addition, the use of offers and live streams to convince the public was significant, supporting the idea that digital interactivity increases customer engagement and loyalty. However, a considerable percentage still do not use the latter tools, suggesting opportunities to boost innovation in digital strategies. (Merino Cava & Valdiviezo Sir, 2022) (Díaz Calle et al., 2024; Lozano-Torres et al., 2021; Mera-Plaza et al., 2022)

In terms of satisfaction, the predominance of "likes" and comments reflects that companies maintain active and two-way communication with their customers, thus facilitating the construction of community and trust. The lower use of surveys and online events could indicate an underexploitation of mechanisms to obtain feedback and personalize the customer experience, a key aspect for differentiation in competitive markets. (Mera-Plaza et al., 2022) (Caro-Moscoso et al., 2021; Shocking -Condori & Molina Díaz, 2020)

The positive impact of advertising campaigns on increasing sales and improving positioning is consistent with research that highlights the reach and effectiveness of social media to promote products in mass consumption sectors. However, the limited adoption of live shopping events poses challenges and opportunities to increase real-time sales and direct interaction, strategies that have shown success in global digital markets. (Shocking -Condori & Molina Díaz, 2020; Romero Medina & Mesías

Cabezas, 2022; Zambrano Macias, 2022) (Arregocés-Mendoza, 2020; Hugo Cardenas et al., 2019)

Regarding internal management, the extensive optimization of orders through social networks and training to improve customer service suggest a growing integration of digital tools in daily operations, a crucial aspect for efficiency and consumer satisfaction. Likewise, the promotion of well-being and a positive organizational culture are key practices to maintain the motivation and commitment of the work team, reinforcing business sustainability. (Hugo Cardenas et al., 2019; Velasco-Arias & Cevallos-Campoverde, 2023) (Castro-Martínez & Díaz-Morilla, 2021)

Supporting SMART objectives as the key to success and implementing strategies that include relevant content, effective advertising, and exclusive promotions, demonstrate increasingly mature strategic planning in these organizations, aligned with the principles of modern business management. However, the disparity in the adoption of certain practices indicates the need for training processes and specialized advice to maximize the use of the full potential offered by social networks. (Castro-Martínez & Díaz-Morilla, 2021; Janssen, 2024)

6. Conclusions

The conclusions obtained in this research show that the strategic use of social networks plays a fundamental and transformative role in fast food companies in the municipality of Tota, Boyacá. First, it is highlighted that innovation and adaptation to change are significant achievements linked to the use of these digital platforms, which underscores the ability of social networks to energize internal and external processes, making it easier for businesses to respond with agility to the demands of the contemporary market. This transformation not only boosts competitiveness, but also positions companies as relevant players within the digital ecosystem.

In terms of customer acquisition and persuasion, the evidence shows that the development of relevant and attractive content is a key factor that guarantees effective attraction, since 100% of companies confirmed its use as a main strategy. In addition, other tools such as offers and live broadcasts complement and reinforce this strategy, expanding the influence and reach of brands in the different segments of the target audience. This shows that the versatility of social media allows traditional marketing techniques to be combined with digital innovations that amplify business impact.

Customer satisfaction is another fundamental aspect that is enhanced by the constant and authentic interaction with users, evidenced by the high number of likes, comments and direct messages received. Genuine communication through stories and exclusive content fosters trust and commitment, essential elements for loyalty in an

increasingly competitive and changing environment. This type of interaction goes beyond simple promotion, generating digital communities that sustain long-term growth.

In the management space, social media drives optimization in order management and operational capabilities through formalized training programs. These actions not only improve efficiency, but also promote a favorable work environment, with practices that support the physical and mental well-being of employees, thus contributing to a healthily productive organizational culture. The importance of these internal factors is key to sustaining progress and comprehensively addressing the challenges associated with digitalisation.

The use of SMART objectives and the implementation of well-structured advertising campaigns were presented as determining factors for success, as they allow to direct efforts clearly and measure results effectively. This reinforces the need for companies to adopt digital management systems that contemplate strategic planning aligned with their resources and goals, guaranteeing the sustainability of growth and the ability to overcome in a dynamic market.

7. Recommendations

The recommendations derived from the results obtained in this research for fast food companies in the municipality of Tota, Boyacá, are the following:

Strengthen continuous training in digital marketing and social media management to improve efficiency in the creation of engaging content, advertising campaigns and use of interactive tools such as live broadcasts and surveys, thus increasing customer attraction and loyalty.

Diversify and deepen authentic communication strategies with customers, encouraging active participation by organizing online events and implementing surveys to better understand the preferences and expectations of the target audience.

Optimize the integration of purchases and direct payments on social networks, enhancing the fluid and fast shopping experience, which can translate into higher sales volumes and consumer satisfaction.

Encourage practices aimed at the physical and mental well-being of staff, such as flexible schedules, promotion of active breaks and a positive organizational culture, to keep employees motivated and engaged, which directly impacts the quality of service.

Adopt and maintain SMART objectives to guide digital planning, ensuring clear, measurable, and achievable goals that facilitate performance evaluation and informed decision-making for continuous improvement.

Implement monitoring and evaluation systems for advertising campaigns, to measure their real impact on sales, visibility and customer satisfaction, allowing agile and effective adjustments to be made in the digital strategy.

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